

- 1) What is online education?-----□
- 2) Is it productive like study on class !-----□
- 3) Best websites to study online-----□
- 4) Where can you practice your acquired skills online--□

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-1) What is online education?

It means that the student receives lessons in the various specializations he wants and can pass proficiency tests also from his home via the Internet only. The lessons consist of video clips, pictures, audio recordings, and even exercises and lessons that can be printed out for more convenience. Online education sources vary, as some register at a university and study remotely according to its curricula, some follow online courses in several fields such as programming and languages, and others hire private instructors and specify the method of study, daily hours, and the total duration of the course.

-2) Is it productive like studying in class?

Currently, it is not possible to be certain that it is better to study in person or via the Internet, because the latter is considered a recent development due to the emerging virus in 2019, but I will try to clear the picture by presenting each type's positive and negative points

-Advantages of studying in attendance :

- * The student benefits from the academic environment of doctors and students, which occupies his focus in the academic environment.
- * Students are obligated to attend class, otherwise, they will be penalized with a points deduction, ensuring that they get all the lessons.
- * The student has the full ability to discuss ideas and questions with the doctor and other students in a comfortable atmosphere away from distractions and interruptions.
- * Students are tested with attendance tests and under the supervision of doctors, which reduces cheating rates.

-Disadvantages of studying in attendance :

- * Some students may have to travel great distances to reach the university and sometimes they arrive late for several reasons beyond their control.
- * The school environment is naturally full of people, and this means constant noise, which disturbs some students who want to study in complete silence.
- * Going and returning daily to the university may be stressful for some students, which does not allow them to review the lessons when they return home, but rather spend their time resting or entertaining their tiring day.
- * Studying at the university needs to pay its premiums, and this is what some students may not be able to afford, especially since they are without a job.

-Advantages of studying online :

- * Studying online is easy, as it is enough just to open the application for the lecture and start studying.
- * Studying online came to remove all the fatigue related to going to university in person and back by studying at home.
- * It gives students the freedom to manage their daily time.
- * The student can have complete peace of mind to study, and this is what studying from home provides.

-Disadvantages of studying online :

- * Studying via the Internet can be interrupted as soon as the Internet is not available or interrupted due to natural reasons or periodic maintenance, which affects the course of the study program.
- * Students can circumvent the doctors by placing a picture or video of them in front of the camera while they are doing other activities such as playing video games or browsing social media.
- * There is a lot of distraction in the house, especially with the availability of comfort and entertainment.
- * Cheating abounds in-home exams by manipulating the exam site to get the answer, or students tell each other the a

nswers.

In short, the in-person study is the best so far, while you are waiting for maintenance of issues related to online study, especially since it has only been updated in the past 3 years.

-3) Best websites to study online :

- Udemy :

It is considered one of the best online learning platforms because it contains different types of courses, some of which are theoretical and applied in countless fields such as programming, cooking, or even painting. There are free and paid courses, and you can benefit from the support of the course owner by asking him questions and he answers them directly. Upon completion of each course, you will receive a certificate that you can add to your resume.

- Coursera :

Coursera has more than 200 universities and elegant company partners, and they believe that learning is the key to human progress, and there you find leading universities around the world that offer online courses to help people improve their educational levels and obtain other certificates that will improve their lives or even their level of Living by working online.

- Skillshare :

Skillshare is an online platform that helps online learners to get where they want to go, they can interact with teachers and other students to share experiences and knowledge and you can even become a teacher on this platform.

-4) Where you can practice your knowledge :

After obtaining the certificate in the skill that you studied via the Internet, you must apply exercises to consolidate your knowledge and become more professional in your skill. There are several ways to apply what you have learned,

the first of which is education through virtual reality glasses, which is a service developed by several websites on the Internet where it provides you with a stage and people interact with you through virtual reality. Secondly, you can apply projects if you have learned programming and the like, on several sites that support programming via the Internet, and after you have mastered the project and studied it in all respects, you can put it on the market and start your entrepreneurial journey, Or you can register on freelancing websites online and start earning your first dollars online.

Science today has not remained a monopoly on books and schools only but has become in every corner of the Internet. It is enough to search for a topic and you will find thousands of results in front of you to learn from. Although abundance is a blessing, it is a curse at the same time. With the abundance of quarries, you cannot distinguish between what is true and false. For this reason, schools are still standing and books are printed and sold on the shelves of offices because they are the origin of all this development in the field of technology and science.